

AREA, PRODUCTION AND PRODUCTIVITY OF PADDY IN ANANTHAPURAMU DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH

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Abstract

Paddy is the most important food crop of India covering about one-fourth of the total cropped area and providing food to about half of the Indian population. This is the staple food of the people living in the eastern and the southern parts of the country, particularly in the areas having over 150 cm annual rainfall. There are about 10,000 varieties of rice in the world out of which about 4,000 are grown in India

Rice is the Principal food crop cultivated throughout the state providing food for its growing population fodder to the cattle and employment to the rural masses. Any decline in its hectarage and production will have a perceivable impact on the state's economy and food security. In A.P rice is mostly cultivated under irrigated eco-system under Canals (52%), Tube Wells (19.31) Tanks (16.2%), other Wells (8.8%) and other sources (3.7%).

In Andhra Pradesh rice is the major food crop grown in 34.59 lakh hectares producing 144.0 lakh.t in both Kharif and Rabi seasons with an average productivity of 3.29 t/ha during 2012- 13. At national level A.P is contributing 12.7% of rice production with 9.08% rice area. The increase in rice area, production and productivity mainly depends on the rainfall and availability of irrigation.

KEY WORDS: Paddy, Cultivation, Prices of Paddy, Farmers Problems

INTRODUCTION

Anantapur is one of the four districts of Rayalaseema region of Andhra Pradesh, the other three being Kurnool, Cuddapah and Chittoor. This region is a typical dry tract of the State situated in an unfavourable natural zone and forms a substantial part of the drought prone region of the State. Anantapuramu district is chemically drought prone area and economically the most valuable part of Andhra Pradesh.

To be more explicit, the district is the second driest part of the country, next of the Thar Desert. The frequent occurrence of drought prolonged dry spells and crop failures have a shattering effect on agriculture of the district.

There is a dire need to study the existing agricultural systems in order to suggest for the planning for the further development of agricultural economy of drought prone areas of the states.

Agriculture sector plays an important role in the economy of the District. The 70 % of the District population depends on Agriculture for their livelihood. The share of Agriculture and allied sectors in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the district ranges from 24.25%.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Paddy cultivators have been facing various problems as their paddy did not fetch the reasonable price all over the country. The fall in the price, increase in cost of cultivation especially increase in the price of fertilizer, severely affect the farmers. Due to the low prices, the farmers get very poor income; this leads to the farmers to avail loans from the local money lenders. The non repayment of loans to both banks and local money lenders forced them to commit suicide. In many parts of the country farmers were committed suicide that could number more than 1000 in last ten years. Andhra Pradesh is one among the states producing paddy to a considerable quantity, and this state also depicts the same picture i.e., the number of farmers commit suicide has been increasing. The causes vary among

according to climatic condition, low price, high cost of cultivation etc. In Andhra Pradesh, the main cause for this extreme condition is low income from farm activity.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To know the sources of irrigation and the area under paddy in Andhra Pradesh.
2. To study the cropping pattern and the production and productivity of paddy in the study area.
3. To evaluate the cost of production and profitability of paddy in the study area and
4. To assess the income and employment generation through paddy cultivation.
5. To understand the problems of paddy cultivators.

Review of literature

Economic Survey (2011), *Planning Commission*, Government of India and for a detailed discussion on the general economic development of India in the recent past, see for instance, Mohana Rao. L.K, budget Meet 2011 held at Dept. of Economics, Andhra University on 5th April 2011.

Joshi (2010)⁴ has also pointed out that intensive agriculture and excessive use of external inputs are leading to degradation of soil, water and genetic resources and negatively effecting agricultural production.

Prabhakaran (2009) has discussed that Palakkad called the rice bowl of Kerala, accounted for nearly 50 per cent of paddy produced in the state during 2008-2009. During 2007-2008, its share was 46 per cent. The increase is attributed to a rise in the area of cultivated land and productivity, said to be the results of a decade – long “silent revolution” initiated by local bodies, government agencies and farmers. The development of eight high – yielding varieties paddy from near extinct traditional varieties of Palakkad has also being to double production the author said.

Pouchepparadjou et al. (2005) examined the economics of paddy cultivation of IPM adopted and non-adopted farms of Union Territory of Pondicherry. It was observed that the IPM adopted farms generated net returns worth of Rs. 5,208 per acre as against Rs. 4,147 per acre net returns of non-adopted farms, which was 26 per cent higher than the non adopted farms.

Nasurudeen and Mahesh (2004) compared the economics of rice cultivation in Karaikal region of Pondicherry (UT). They found that total cost per hectare was Rs. 15,040 and Rs. 19735 for direct sown paddy and transplanted paddy, respectively. The yield level was found to be more in the case of transplanted paddy (4185 kg/ha) than that in the direct sown paddy (3590 kg/ha). However, net returns were more for direct sown paddy (Rs. 6500/ha) than for the transplanted paddy (Rs. 5375/ha). In spite of the low yield level direct sown paddy proved to be more profitable as it reduced the requirement of resource and cost of cultivation.

METHODOLOGY AND SAMPLING DESIGN

Multi-stage random sampling has been adopted for sampling design. Three revenue divisions of the Ananthapuramu District, i.e. Kalyanadurgam, Anantapuramu and Kadiri are considered. In the first stage, one mandal from each revenue division has been selected i.e. Garladinne in Ananthapuramu Revenue Division, Kanekal in Kalyanadurgam Revenue Division and Nallamada in Kadiri Revenue Division, are the area under paddy cultivation is relatively high in the concerned divisions. In the second stage, 12 revenue villages representing three revenue mandals, i.e. 4 villages from each mandal are selected for the present study. Village wise and category wise i.e. marginal, small, medium and large farmers list has been prepared for the selection of sample households. Finally, 25 sample respondents from each revenue village covering all social groups were selected for the purpose of the study by using random numbers.

The total sample size of the present study is (100. of the total 300 sample households, a total of 100 sample households are selected from each mandal. 28 marginal farmers, 28 small farmers, 28 medium farmers and 16 large

farmers are covered from each mandal and thus totaling of 84 marginal farmers, 84 small farmers, 84 medium farmers and 48 large farmers in the study area.

Paddy is the principal crop extensively cultivated in all the districts of the state both in Kharif and Rabi seasons. It accounted for 29.8 percent of the total cropped area, 69.1 percent of the total food grains production during 2012-13. The area under the paddy during 2001-02 was 38.25 lakh hectares as against 36.28 lakh hectares in the previous year regarding a decreasing. The area under the paddy was the highest in the last five years due to favorable seasonal conditions during south- west monsoon period. The production of paddy during 2001-02 was 113.09 lakh tonnes against 115.11 lakh tonnes in 2012-13 regarding an increased. The yield rate of paddy as gone down to 2978 kgs/hectare in 2001-02 from 3173 kgs/hectare in 2012-13 due to increased. The paddy area was affected by severe floods/cyclones last five years due to favorable seasonal conditions during south- west monsoon period.

TABLE. 1
Area, Production and Productivity of Paddy in Andhra Pradesh

YEARS	Paddy		
	Area	Production	Productivity
2001-2002	38.25	113.90	2978
2002-2003	28.22	73.27	2597
2003-2004	29.75	89.53	3011
2004-2005	30.86	96.01	3111
2005-2006	39.82	117.04	2939
2010-2011	40.24	225.36	3152
2011-12	40.96	128.92	3148
2012-13	36.28	115.11	3173

Source: Seasons and crop Report of Andhra Pradesh 2010-11.

NOTE: Area in lakh hectares; production in lakh tonnes, productivity in kgs/hectares.

Figure .1 Bar diagram sowing Area, Production and Productivity of Paddy in Andhra Pradesh

PROBLEMS OF PADDY FARMERS

The farmers of the study villages have been facing various problems and the list of problems told by the farmers has given in table 2. Many farmers have multiple problems but their prime problem has been taken for the analysis. In all, nearly 70 per cent of the farmers told that there is shortage of labour. This alone is the prime problem, and some times the farmers put their land as follow due to this problem. The next important problem in the study region is lackof water storage (10%). However, it was not at all a problem among the farmers of Kaneka village as they have good water storage facility. All other problems viz. higher wage, natural calamities, low price for paddy, and water availability are the minor ones among the paddy cultivators. All the villages have shown the same picture with labour shortage as the primary problem

SOURCES OF IRRIGATION

The main sources of irrigation in the district are wells, Canals and tanks Canal water is supplied through major and medium irrigation projects. Tanks have been providing irrigation facilities since the time immemorial. Other sources include inundation canals, different lifting systems of water from rivers, streams etc. Table 3.6 presents the particulars of area irrigated in Anantapur district by different sources. The net irrigated area was 82,614 hectares in 1960-61 and it increased to 1,77,146 hectares in 2001-2002 registering a 2.14 fold increase after a long period of forty years. But it declined to 1,37,419 hectares in 2006-2007. The data presented in Table 3.6 clearly indicates that wells are the chief source of irrigation in the district followed by canals and tanks. As high as 84.28 percent of net irrigated area in 2002-2003 was served by wells. This indicates the importance of wells in providing irrigation facilities to agriculture.

Table. 2
Source-wise Irrigated Area in Anantapuramu District

(Area in Hectares)

Year	Wells	Percent to total	Canals	Percent to total	Tanks	Percent to total	Other sources	Percent to total	Total
1960-61	26452	32.02	17717	21.44	36745	44.48	1700	2.06	82614
1970-71	49607	39.43	42167	33.52	31727	25.22	2300	1.83	125801
1980-81	64109	56.41	31196	27.45	12806	11.27	5532	4.87	113643
1990-91	83193	65.35	35671	28.02	5100	4.01	3330	2.62	127294
2000-01	132453	75.57	32196	18.37	5833	3.33	4793	2.73	175275
2001-02	131914	74.47	30539	17.24	10155	5.73	4538	2.56	177146
2002-03	132436	84.28	20469	13.00	2182	1.39	2098	1.33	157185
2003-04	116863	82.41	22621	15.95	1718	1.21	608	0.43	141810
2004-05	112903	79.65	26513	18.70	1125	0.80	1210	0.85	141751
2005-06	113379	73.81	30164	19.64	8105	5.28	1958	1.27	153606
2006-07	111111	80.86	23868	17.37	1869	1.36	571	0.41	137419
2007-08	118790	78.41	25363	16.74	5403	3.57	1934	1.28	151490

Source: Hand book of statistics, office of the chief planning officer, Anantapuramu.

The area irrigated by canals decreased from 33.52 percent in 1970-71 to 16.74 percent in 2007-2008. By over all observation, area irrigated under canals decreased during the period shown in the table. It is also evident that canals are not providing irrigation facilities to the total area of land brought under canals. But canals occupy second place in providing irrigation facilities to agriculture.

Tanks occupy the last place in providing irrigation facilities in Anantapuramu district. Irrigation under tanks was significant between 1960-61 and 1970-71. Because the share of tanks in total irrigated area was 44.48 percent and 25.22 percent respectively. The area irrigated by tanks showed a declining trend and there were fluctuations in irrigated area.

Because tanks are completely neglected and many of them are silted. Another important reason is low rainfall. Since the rainfall is scare and uneven in distribution the rivers and streams which are rain-fed don't provide sufficient water for surface irrigation. Because of this reason the demand for ground water increased by constructing more number of bore wells. One can clearly observe this in Anantapuramu district. Agriculturists of Anantapuramu district practice double cropping and multiple cropping. That means they grow corps in Kharif, Rabi and Summer seasons. Without sufficient irrigation facilities double and multiple cropping is not possible.

SUGGESTIONS FOR PADDY CULTIVATORS

In relation to suggestions of the farmers a list of it were presented in table3. Each farmer has their own suggestions and most of them have not suggested anything. Thus 32 per cent of the paddy cultivators have not given any suggestion to improve the production of paddy. However, the same proportion of farmers suggested that subsidy for paddy cultivation will increase the production to a greater extent. Some of the farmers (18%), have suggested that high yielding varieties of seeds will increase the paddy production. About 10 per cent of the farmers have suggested that proper mechanization will reduce the labour shortage which in turn leads to higher production. This overall suggestions has been noticed in all the villages of the present study.

CONCLUSIONS

Paddy cultivation in Nallamada is falling down over the period of time. The major causative factor identified by the social scientists is a shortage of labour and low price for paddy. This statement has been proved in the present study. Though the fertility of the soil, favorable monsoon, and government policies have helped the farmers they have not completely engaged in paddy cultivation as it requires timely manual work. This needs more human labour, which is the only problem among the farmers. And hence, mechanization, or participation of more human labour alone will increase the paddy production in the study area

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